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Time-Resolved Analysis of the Structural Dynamics of Assembling Gold Nanoparticles

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3 ABSTRACT
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5 The hydrophobic collapse is a structural transition of grafted
6 polymer chains in a poor solvent. Although such a transition seems
7 an intrinsic event during clustering of polymer-stabilized
8 nanoparticles in the liquid phase, it has not been resolved in
9 real time. In this work, we implemented a microfluidic 3D-flow-
10 focusing mixing reactor equipped with real-time analytics, small-
11 angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy, to
12 study the early stage of cluster formation, for polystyrene-
13 stabilized gold nanoparticles. The polymer shell dynamics obtained
14 by *in situ* SAXS analysis and numerical simulation of the solvent
15 composition allowed us to map the interaction energy between the
16 particles at early state of solvent mixing, 30 ms behind the
17 crossing point. We found that the rate of hydrophobic collapse
18 depends on water concentration, ranging between 100 and 500 nm/s.
19 Importantly, we found that the polymer shell collapses prior to
20 the commencement of clustering.
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KEYWORDS

Gold nanoparticles, self-assembly, microfluidics, small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), hydrophobic collapse, hydrophobic interactions, real-time analytics

Solvent-induced self-assembly of nanoparticles, driven by hydrophobic interactions in a liquid phase, is a convenient strategy to fabricate complex architectures in a bottom-up fashion.¹ Polystyrene-stabilized gold nanoparticles (Au@PS) of different shapes - spheres,^{2,3} rods,⁴⁻⁶ stars,⁷ cubes^{8,9} and wires¹⁰ - have been used to build a variety of structures including spherical clusters,^{11,12} dynamic chain-like assemblies,^{13,14} vesicles,^{15,16} or low-symmetry dimers.¹⁷ Since the major part of these architectures are kinetic products,¹⁸ their structure (*e.g.* number and distribution of nanoparticles per cluster) and quality depends on the way the non-solvent (water) is added to a dispersion of nanoparticles which are coated with a radially-distributed polymer shell in a good solvent (DMF, THF). It has been reported that water addition induces the so-called *hydrophobic collapse*,¹⁹ a transition from random coil to compact globule of the grafted polymer, which eventually leads to the formation of regio-specific polymeric patches or compact shells on the surface of the inorganic cores.²⁰ Although the hydrophobic collapse of grafted polymers is well-

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3 understood at a single molecule level, it remains poorly investigated in colloidal systems during
4 the self-assembly process. Of particular relevance are the questions on (1) how fast the polymer
5 shell collapses and (2) how fast the particles agglomerate in reaction to this effect.
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11 To study the dynamics of surface phenomena and self-assembly in the response to the
12 environmental changes several requirements should be met: (1) ensuring reproducible and
13 controllable solvent mixing (water, THF), (2) knowing the exact concentration of solvents and
14 nanoparticles, and (3) implementing real-time analytics. Microfluidic devices provides a suitable
15 experimental environment to meet the above requirements.²¹ In fact, Nie and coworkers have
16 exploited a flow-focusing system for the self-assembly of nanoparticles through controlled solvent
17 mixing, thereby achieving assemblies in the form of vesicles.¹⁵ Kraus and coworkers have recently
18 demonstrated that the incorporation of online small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and UV-Vis
19 spectroscopy (both at the outlet of the chip) can provide meaningful insights on the mechanisms
20 behind the clustering process at different temperatures.²² However, the incorporation of *on-chip*
21 analytical tools for *in situ* studies involves additional complexity, since a flow reactor requires a
22 unique design and the use of adequate materials to minimize the interference with the selected
23 analytical method.^{23–25} Therefore, efforts are required to implement *on-chip* analytical tools, in
24 order to get an insight on the early stage of the clustering of gold nanoparticles through
25 hydrophobic forces.
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48 We show here that solvent-induced collapse of grafted polystyrene on gold nanoparticles occurs
49 before clustering commences. We designed and fabricated a 3D flow-focusing microfluidic device
50 which ensured spatially-resolved mixing conditions of water and nanoparticles in THF or DMF.
51 Off-chip online UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy and *ex situ* TEM analysis confirmed highly
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3 reproducible and fluctuation-free clustering of nanoparticles over a wide range of experimental
4 conditions. The incorporation of on-chip SAXS analysis allowed us to resolve the dynamics of
5 polymer shell collapse upon self-assembly experimentally, supported by theoretical analysis of the
6 interaction energy landscape at steady-state conditions.
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17 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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19 In order to study how fast the polymer shell collapses and particle agglomerates form, our
20 microfluidic reactor was designed to precisely trigger this process via rapid mixing in a 3D-
21 hydrodynamic flow focusing geometry.²⁶ First of all, focusing the sample down to a narrow
22 laminar stream allows for fast diffusion-based mixing due to the reduced length scales.²⁷ Second,
23 the continuous flow enables mapping the reaction time points onto specific positions along the
24 microchannel, which, in combination with microfocused X-ray beam scanning orthogonally to the
25 flow and the lateral focusing directions (see **Figure 1B**), enables the collection of time-resolved
26 structural data of the centrally focused sample with high spatial and temporal resolution.^{23,24} For
27 this purpose, we produced a completely Kapton®-based microfluidic device that was solvent-
28 compatible, X-ray transparent and, therefore, ideally-suited for *in situ* small-angle X-ray scattering
29 measurements.²⁶ The device fabrication was based on previously described work combining laser
30 ablation^{24,28} and covalent bonding.^{26,29,30} and it was equipped with online UV-Vis-NIR
31 spectroscopy (**Figures 1a and S1**). The microreactor was connected to three gas-tight syringes:
32 the main channel syringe contained a THF dispersion of Au@PS while the two lateral side channel
33 syringes supplied a mixture of THF and water ($\phi_{sc}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 21 \text{ vol}\%$). In all experiments, we used
34 Au@PS of $46.9 \pm 2.0 \text{ nm}$ in core diameter, $[\text{Au}] = 25 \text{ mM}$, covered with thiolated polystyrene
35 ($M_w = 53 \text{ kg/mol}$), synthesized following our previous report¹¹ (**Figure S2**). The microfluidic
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3 reactor featured a cross-shaped geometry where the sample solution in the main channel enters the
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5 flow focusing region through a centrally-placed spherical pore with a diameter of 30 μm to avoid
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7 wall contact of the sample along the reaction channel. The sample solution is hydrodynamically
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9 flow focused into a narrow stream through sheathing by the laterally-incoming fluids from the two
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11 perpendicular side channels. The combined flow then enters the reaction channel (width: 120 μm ,
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13 height: 125 μm) which extended over 47.5 mm behind the mixing cross.^{24,26,27} The width of the
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15 flow-focused, or sheathed, sample stream, w_f , depends on the reaction channel width, w_r , and flow
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17 rates of the main (Q_{mc}) and the lateral side channel inlets (Q_{sc1} and Q_{sc2}):^{23,26}
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$$20 \quad 21 \quad 22 \quad 23 \quad 24 \quad 25 \quad 26 \quad 27 \quad 28 \quad 29 \quad 30 \quad 31 \quad 32 \quad 33 \quad 34 \quad 35 \quad 36 \quad 37 \quad 38 \quad 39 \quad 40 \quad 41 \quad 42 \quad 43 \quad 44 \quad 45 \quad 46 \quad 47 \quad 48 \quad 49 \quad 50 \quad 51 \quad 52 \quad 53 \quad 54 \quad 55 \quad 56 \quad 57 \quad 58 \quad 59 \quad 60$$

$$w_f = \frac{Q_{mc}}{Q_{sc1} + Q_{mc} + Q_{sc2}} w_r = \frac{1}{FRR + 1} w_r \quad (1)$$

where FRR relates to flow rate ratio, $FRR = (Q_{sc1} + Q_{sc2})/Q_{mc}$.¹⁵ Thus, the limiting values of the
width of the focused stream range from 40 to 11 μm , for $FRR = 2$ and 10, respectively. The values
for w_f were verified theoretically via finite element-based computation fluid dynamics (CFD)
simulations (see **Figure S8**), as well as experimentally.^{23,26}

The laminar flow conditions (Reynolds number $Re = 2.3$) and narrow flow focusing on the micron-
scale in our reactor allows for fast diffusion-based mixing.^{27,31} Combined with the 3D-flow
focusing in the center of the parabolic flow profile, these experimental conditions ensure a
controlled clustering process driven by diffusion where the distance along the flow channel
corresponds to the time axis. Based on Fick's laws of diffusion, the mean square displacement in
the y direction, perpendicular to the flow in x direction, is given by ^{24,26}

$$\Delta y = \sqrt{2Dt} \quad (2)$$

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3 Thus, by taking into account the diffusion coefficients of interdiffusing solvents and particles, D
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5 ($D_{\text{water}} = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, $D_{\text{THF}} = 0.9 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, $D_{\text{AuNP}} \approx 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$),^{24,26} the channel geometry
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7 and the applied flow rates, one can estimate the mean diffusion time t , at which diffusional
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9 transport will have occurred across half the microfluidic channel.^{24,26} Thus, for $FRR = 2$ and total
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11 volumetric flow rate $Q_{\text{tot}} = 900 \mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ corresponding to an average velocity of $v =$
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13 (Q_{tot}/wh) = 16.7 mm/s, one can easily find that diffusional transport across the distance
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15 $w_f/2 = 20.8 \mu\text{m}$ will have occurred after $t_{D(\text{THF})} = 0.22 \text{ s}$, corresponding to a downstream position
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17 of $\Delta x = vt = 3.6 \text{ mm}$ behind the crossing point for THF and water. This means that complete
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19 diffusional mixing in the flow-focusing experiment resulting in a homogeneous solvent mixture
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21 across the channel will have occurred *after* this distance, while a significant concentration jump is
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23 already expected shortly thereafter.^{27,31} This solvent mixing behavior was also confirmed by our
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25 COMSOL CFD simulations which coupled Navier-Stokes equations for the flow field with Fick's
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27 laws of diffusion (*vide infra* **Figure 4**).^{24,26} On the other hand, the diffusion of Au@PS
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29 nanoparticles across the channel, regardless of the FRR value, will only be a few micrometers over
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31 the whole experimental time scale and can therefore be neglected.²⁴ Finally, the design of our flow
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33 reactor imposes certain constraints in the implementation of real-time analytics. For example, to
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35 avoid clogging of the channel due to excessive exposure to the beam during on-chip SAXS
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37 measurements, one should keep $FRR > 2$. On the other hand, the online UV-Vis-NIR
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39 measurements are convenient at lower values of FRR , between 0.1 and 4, since at $FRR > 4$ the
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41 dilution of Au@PS in the flowing mixture rules out the detection of nanoparticles by optical
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Figure 1. Design of a 3D flow focusing reactor for studying nanoparticles self-assembly. a) Polystyrene-coated gold nanoparticles in THF undergo clustering upon mixing with water in a Kapton®-based hydrodynamic 3D flow-focusing reactor. Real-time UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy in flow collects the optical properties of the assemblies at the reactor outlet. On-chip SAXS analysis along the channel (orthogonally to the flow and the lateral focusing directions) allows us to determine time-resolved structural changes of the polymer shell and clustering nanoparticles upon mixing. **b)** Simulated (COMSOL CFD) longitudinal cross-section of the THF/water mixture and dimensions of the reactor. Volumetric flow rates of middle channel (Q_{mc}) and side channels (Q_{sc}).

To study the hydrophobic collapse of the polymer shell during self-assembly, we first ensured fluctuation-free clustering at different solvent compositions. We performed six cycles of nanoparticles clustering in the flow-focusing microchannel by varying the FRR between 0 and 2 at $Q_{tot} = 600 \mu\text{L/h}$ (water content was varied between 0 and 14 vol%, for FRR 0 and 2, respectively) (**Figure 2a, S3**). In an experiment lasting over 3 hours (~3600 spectra in total), the

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3 localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) was fully recovered at each aggregation cycle. To
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5 gain more detailed information on the optical fingerprints at given FRR values, we processed the
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7 whole dataset (Matlab) by extracting the LSPR maximum (λ_{\max}) and the full width at half
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9 maximum (FWHM) (**Figure 2b**). By changing the FRR from 0 (no water) to 2, λ_{\max} and FWHM
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11 changed from 532 to 555 nm and from 60 to 80 nm, respectively, as expected for nanoparticles
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13 aggregation where a significant interparticle distance is maintained, so that the obtained shift is
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15 relatively small. These results were also confirmed by TEM analysis, as shown in **Figure 2b, c**.
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17 We observed that FWHM values experienced slight fluctuations upon clustering (FRR = 2) due to
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19 the formation of gas microbubbles, which are characteristic for a mixture containing low boiling
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21 point solvents such as THF.^{32,33} Such a reasoning was further confirmed by using DMF as a
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23 solvent, which indeed improved the stability of the spectral features (**Figure S4**).
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29 While the spectral features showed excellent stability, the transition between limiting values
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31 occurred with a temporal delay, as compared to changes of the input *FRR*. Although the estimated
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33 mean residence time, t_{res} , equals 1.5 min, the *FRR* transition from 0 to 2 was delayed,
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35 $\Delta t_1 = 3.2$ min. The reverse transition (from 2 to 0) took even a longer time: $\Delta t_2 = 6.1$ min
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37 (**Figure 2b, grey rectangles**). The difference in Δt_1 and Δt_2 at a given *FRR* transition was due to
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39 the inhomogeneous distribution of aggregates over the channel cross-section.³⁴ Put differently,
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41 aggregates with a longer residence time (*FRR* = 2) require more time to exit the reactor and
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43 therefore contribute to the overall optical response for a longer time.
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Figure 2. Online optical UV-vis-NIR and off-chip TEM characterization of clustered gold nanoparticles. **a)** Normalized UV-Vis-NIR spectra in flow, during cyclic clustering by switching the flow rate ratio, FRR , between 0 (dispersed) and 2 (aggregated), at a total flow rate of $Q_{tot} = 600 \mu\text{L/h}$. Each spectrum was recorded in an interval of 3 s. **b)** Extracted spectral features of three consecutive clustering cycles between $FRR = 0$ and 2, showing reproducible values of the spectral features. **c)** TEM images of dispersed and aggregated nanoparticles (Scale bars: 200 nm). **d)** Changes of spectral features as a function of FRR showing that $FRR = 0.3$ is the limiting ratio between water and THF. Error bars are standard deviations calculated from 100 data points after flow stabilization. **e)** TEM images of clustered nanoparticles for $FRR = 0.5$ and 4 (Scale bars: 500 nm).

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3 A flow device with automated feeding system allowed us to screen experimental parameters in a
4 single run, with a minimal amount of sample. We tuned FRR values from 0.1 to 4 in 7 consecutive
5 steps, using FRR = 0 as a washing step. We found that clustering commences above FRR = 0.3 (5
6 vol% water, [AuNPs] = 19.2 mM), which is in good agreement with our recent work on clustering
7 in batch conditions (**Figures 2d,e and S3**).¹² The increase of FRR to 0.5 (7 vol% water, [Au] =
8 16.7 mM) led to a significant LSPR redshift, from 532 to 554 nm, and band broadening from 60
9 to 101 nm. At FRR ranging from 1 to 4 (further increase of water and decrease of Au@PS
10 concentration), LSPR maximum and FWHM stabilized at ~550 nm and ~80 nm, respectively. At
11 low FRR (low water vol% and high concentration of nanoparticles) a large number of clusters
12 form, which can experience gradual growth by incorporation of individual nanoparticles with
13 relatively extended polymer shells, leading to the formation of large clusters at the end of the
14 channel. At higher FRR (increase of water vol% and decrease of nanoparticle concentration), a
15 small number of clusters form, which remain kinetically frozen (high amount of water), with
16 collapsed polymer shells. Further growth of these clusters is prevented because of the limited
17 amount of individual nanoparticles. The observed tendency correlates well with previous
18 observations on the self-assembly of phospholipids in flow focusing devices to produce vesicles.³⁵
19 Worth mentioning is the fact that the effect of FRR on particles clustering is solvent independent;
20 in DMF the general trend was preserved, but instead of spherical clusters chain-like structures
21 formed, of different lengths depending on the applied FRR (**Figure S5**). To further support our
22 reasoning, we conducted control experiments by varying water content and nanoparticle
23 concentration, at constant FRR = 0.5. We observed that, for a wide range of water content, the
24 spectral features remained unchanged, while the increase of nanoparticle concentration from 8.3
25 to 20.6 mM (at constant FRR) caused an LSPR redshift from 550 to 560 nm, as well as an increase
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3 of FWHM values (**Figure S6**). Bearing these results in mind, we selected FRR as the main
4 experimental parameter to measure the hydrophobic collapse by using SAXS.
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8 To study an early stage of the clustering process, we implemented on-chip SAXS characterization
9 for different values of *FRR*, ranging from 0 to 10. The SAXS scans were performed at the ID02
10 beamline (ESRF), where we collected data at 23 different downstream positions along the long
11 axis of the channel, with an X-ray spot size of $80 \times 48 \mu\text{m}^2$. At each downstream position, seven
12 vertical scans were acquired with the center of the X-ray beam covering a range of $\pm 40 \mu\text{m}$ from
13 the center of the channel. The design of our reactor imposes two limiting time scales for the
14 experiments, namely time resolution, t_{min} , and the maximum residence time inside the device, t_{max} .
15 The time resolution t_{min} is given by the size of the X-ray beam in the horizontal direction
16 $\Delta x_{\text{spot}} = 80 \mu\text{m}$, and the average flow velocity of the stream v , as $t_{\text{min}} = \Delta x_{\text{spot}}/v$. For a channel cross-
17 section of $120 \mu\text{m} \times 125 \mu\text{m}$ and a total flow rate of $Q_{\text{tot}} = 900 \mu\text{L/h}$, we obtain an average flow
18 velocity of $v = Q_{\text{tot}}/w \cdot h = 16.7 \text{ mm/s}$, which translates into a time resolution of 4.8 ms. On the
19 other hand, the maximum residence time inside the device, $t_{\text{max}} = l/v$, was estimated from the flow
20 velocity v and the length of the device ($l_c = 47.5 \text{ mm}$), giving $t_{\text{max}} = 2.8 \text{ s}$ for our experimental
21 conditions. Therefore, processes taking place within the $t_{\text{min}} = 1.6 \text{ ms} \leq t \leq t_{\text{max}} = 2.8 \text{ s}$ time
22 window were followed in the experiment.
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25 The 1D scattering curves for Au@PS in pure THF, serving as a control experiment, showed a
26 stable flow of non-aggregating nanoparticles along the channel length (**Figure 3d**). However,
27 significant changes were recorded along the channel in the presence of water (**Figure 3a-c**). As
28 expected, with the increase of *FRR* from 2 to 10, the spectral features appeared at shorter distances
29 behind the crossing point, indicating faster kinetics of interparticle interactions with accelerated
30 solvent mixing, which goes in hand with an increased amount of water (see **Figure S8**).
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Interestingly, the disappearance of the scattering features at longer distances behind the crossing point (especially visible for high $FRR = 10$) suggest a gradual dilution of Au@PS toward the lateral parts of the channel or inhomogeneous distribution of interparticle distances within the cluster.

Figure 3. In situ SAXS characterization of clustering particles. a-c) Scattering curves of flow-focused Au@PS obtained at various downstream channel positions x_c under different flow rate ratios ($FRR = 0, 2, 4, 10$, each with $Q_{tot} = 900 \mu\text{L/h}$). The scattering curves were fitted (red lines) using the hard sphere model for disordered particle assemblies (in Percus-Yevick approximation) indicating the occurrence of interparticle interactions. d) Scattering curves of reference Au@PS in pure THF ($FRR = 0$) showing unaltered spectral features along the channel. e, f) Temporal evolution of the effective particle radius R_{eff} (e) and the hard sphere volume fraction η (f) along the microfluidic channel at $FRR = 2, 4$ and 10 , respectively. Both fit parameters reach an onset (dashed circles), indicating a fast collapse of the polymer shell. The geometrical parameters were obtained by applying the hard sphere model for disordered particle assemblies (Percus-Yevick approximation).

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3 SAXS characterization allowed us to determine the dynamics of the polystyrene shell and the
4 interactions between nanoparticles through the description of the structure factor $S(q)$, which
5 correlates to the measured scattering intensity $I(q)$ as follows:^{36–38}
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$$I(q) = N \cdot \Delta\varphi^2 \cdot V^2 \cdot P(q) \cdot S(q) \quad (3)$$

14 where N is the number of particles per unit volume, $\Delta\varphi$ is the excess scattering length density with
15 respect to the solvent, V is the volume of each particle and $P(q)$ is the form factor related to the
16 scattering of a single particle. The structure factor S relates to the Fourier Transform $C(q)$ of a
17 direct correlation function $c(r)$, which describes the spatial distribution of scattering particles:³⁹
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$$S(q) = \frac{1}{1 - N \cdot c(q)} \quad (4)$$

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28 The structure factor S is expected to change during the clustering process, whereas the absence of
29 interparticle interactions (as for $FRR = 0$) is reflected by $S = 1$.
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34 The fitting of SAXS curves ($I(q)$) for the reference experiment ($FRR = 0$) was performed through
35 the homogeneous sphere model that refers to the inner particle radius and its standard deviation as
36 fitting parameters (**Figure S9**). However, the extended polymer shell of dispersed Au@PSs
37 remained undetectable via SAXS, due to a low scattering contrast between the polystyrene shell
38 and the surrounding solvent (scattering length densities: $SLD_{\text{THF}} = 8.4 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and
39 $SLD_{\text{PS}} = 9.6 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, whereas $SLD_{\text{Au}} = 100 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$; **Figure S7**).³⁶
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49 The fitting of $I(q)$ in the clustering experiments ($FRR = 2, 4, 10$) was performed using the Percus-
50 Yevick approximation, which takes into account the effective radius, R_{eff} , of the interacting
51 particles and the volume fraction of hard spheres, $\eta = 4R_{\text{in}}n/3$, where $R_{\text{in}} = 23.5 \text{ nm}$ is the radius
52 of Au@PSs estimated by TEM analysis.^{39–41} R_{eff} correlates to the minimum distance between gold-
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3 to-gold surfaces ($D = 2[R_{\text{eff}} - R_{\text{in}}]$) or center-to-center ($D_{\text{Au-Au}} = 2R_{\text{eff}}$), thus giving the shell
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5 thickness, $L_{\text{SAXS}} (R_{\text{eff}} = R_{\text{in}} + L_{\text{SAXS}})$.
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9 **Figures 3e and 3f** show the change of R_{eff} and η along the microchannel at $FRR = 2, 4$ and 10 . The
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11 effective radius R_{eff} dropped with increasing the distance from the mixing point, whereas the
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13 volume fraction η increased, which is especially visible for $FRR = 2$. Interestingly, such reverse
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15 tendencies last for 300 ms (5 mm behind crossing point) for both parameters, followed by leveling
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17 off (dashed circles). We postulate that the drop of R_{eff} represents a decrease in the length of the
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19 polymer shell, while the region of maximum η values reflects the moment of completed shell
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21 collapse. Thus, the initial increase of η is due to the increase of the electron density of the polymer
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23 shell since solvent molecules get expelled from the polymer corona, thereby increasing the
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25 scattering contrast of the shell with respect to the solvent. Upon shell collapse, the diffusion of
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27 nanoparticles causes a decrease in the hard sphere volume fraction. For higher FRR values, we
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29 observed that the onset of R_{eff} and maximum points of η shift towards the upstream direction,
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31 indicating that, with a higher amount of water and stronger flow-focusing, the shell collapse and
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33 diffusion-based dilution occur at a faster rate, respectively. At longer distances behind the mixing
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35 point, the values of R_{eff} converge to a minimum, corresponding to a 24 nm gap between the
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37 nanoparticles, as confirmed by TEM analysis (**Figure 2e**).
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45 To obtain the real water concentration at any point of the channel, we performed COMSOL CFD
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47 simulations of the solvent mixing process in a three-dimensional model. The steady-state
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49 incompressible Navier-Stokes equation is coupled with the equations for Fick's laws to describe
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51 the convection and diffusion to model solvent mixing inside the microreactor (**Figure 4a, S8**).^{15,42}
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54 The implemented flow rates (and solvent compositions) of the side and main channel solutions
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were the same as those used in the X-ray scattering experiment ($Q_{\text{tot}} = 900 \mu\text{L/h}$ and $\phi_{\text{sc}}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 21 \text{ vol}\%$ at $FRR = 2, 4, 10$). We found that solvent mixing occurs at very small timescales, in agreement with the SAXS characterization. As visualized in **Figure 4a**, solvent mixing is mostly completed at distances of 5, 2 and $<0.5 \text{ mm}$ behind the mixing cross, for FRR s 2, 4 and 10, respectively. These positions correlate well with the distance of completed polymer shell collapse, after which changes in the scattering curves indicate the onset of clustering.

Figure 4. Mapping interparticle interaction energy over the entire channel length. **a)** Top view of the longitudinal cross section of a simulated distribution of THF concentration in the channel ($l = 47.5 \text{ mm}$), at FRR ranging from 2 to 10 and total flow rate of $Q_{\text{tot}} = 900 \mu\text{L/h}$. **b)** Calculated interaction potential E_{inter} at different channel positions x_c , for $FRR = 2, 4$ and 10. **c,d)** Primary energy minima, E_{min} , and maxima, E_{max} , obtained from **b)** at different positions along the channel, suggesting that the clustering of Au@PS is favored after full collapse of the polystyrene shell.

To further confirm that the hydrophobic collapse occurs before the start of the clustering process, we implemented our recently reported model for the interaction potential energy, which takes into the account brush repulsions, as well as van der Waals (vdW) and hydrophobic attractions:¹¹

$$E_{\text{inter}} = \frac{200R_{\text{in}}L^2k_{\text{B}}T}{\pi s^3} - \frac{R}{6} \left(\frac{A_{232}}{D-2L} - \frac{2A_{123}}{D-L} + \frac{A_{121}}{D} \right) - 4\pi RD_0\gamma(1-f)e^{-\frac{D-2L}{D_0}} \quad (5)$$

where R_{in} is the nanoparticle radius, L is the length of the polymer chain, s is the footprint diameter of a single polymer chain, $A_{232} = A_{\text{PS-THF-PS}}$, $A_{123} = A_{\text{Au-PS-THF}}$ and $A_{121} = A_{\text{Au-PS-Au}}$ are the Hamaker constants, D refers to the distance between gold-to-gold surfaces, γ is the interfacial energy of the polystyrene in a specific solvent composition, D_0 is the hydrophobic decay length and f is the hydrophobic parameter, related to water content. While the polymer length, $L \approx L_{\text{SAXS}}$, was estimated *via* SAXS experiments, the values of γ were estimated according to previous work, assuming a linear dependence of γ with the amount of water.¹¹ Eq. 5 implies that the contribution of hydrophobic interactions reaches a maximum at $f=0$, while at $f=1$ the particles remain dispersed, *i.e.* no hydrophobic interactions. We recently estimated experimentally the values of f , suggesting that 5 and 40 vol% of water in THF corresponds to $f=1$ and 0, respectively (**Figure S10**).¹² In this interval, we assume a linear relation between the hydrophobic parameter f and the amount of water (**Equation S2**).

With the exact information on polymer shell thickness, L , interfacial energy, γ , and f values in hand, we mapped the energy interaction between nanoparticles at different points of the channel, at *FRRs* ranging from 2 to 10, as a function of the interparticle distance $D-2L_{\text{SAXS}}$. **Figure 4b** depicts the interaction potential between nanoparticles at the first 5 mm behind the mixing point. Prior to solvent mixing, clustering is prevented since steric repulsions overcome the vdW

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3 attractions. With increasing the distance behind the crossing point, the amount of water gradually
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5 increases, causing a drop in the energy barrier E_{\max} .
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9 To obtain more detailed information on the interaction energies, we plotted the energy barrier E_{\max}
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11 and the primary minimum at polystyrene-polystyrene contact, E_{\min} , along the channel
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13 (**Figure 4c, d**). As expected, the significant drop of E_{\min} and E_{\max} occurs at the first downstream
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15 position in the channel (<2 mm). Interestingly, the calculation confirms that the value of E_{\min}
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17 depends on the amount of water (FRR) in the given mixture. That is, with an increasing amount of
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19 water, E_{\min} goes to lower values that remain constant with increasing the distance behind the
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21 crossing point. Similarly, the rate of E_{\max} decrease is strongly affected by the flow rate ratio (or
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23 water amount) showing that for $FRR = 2$ the energy barrier (preventing aggregation) experiences
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25 a moderate drop. At higher amounts of water ($FRR = 4$ or 10), the barrier reaches zero values at a
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27 shorter distance behind the crossing point. Importantly, the change in the theoretical value of E_{\max}
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29 correlates well with the experimental values of the effective radius obtained by SAXS
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31 measurements (**Figure 3e**). Both values reached an onset at exactly the same downstream position
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33 for each FRR , bringing thus relevant implications: 1) the clustering process of Au@PS starts
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35 preferentially after both solvents, THF and water, are completely mixed, 2) the clustering of
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37 Au@PS commences once the polymeric shell is fully collapsed. We estimated the rate of polymer
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39 shell collapse, finding that at $FRR = 2$ and 4 , the mean rates of shell thickness collapse, $u_{sc,mean} = \Delta$
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41 $L_{SAXS}/\Delta t$, are 92 and 246 nm/s, respectively. For higher FRR (10), our experimental setup was
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43 unable to resolve the dynamics of shell collapse, but we estimate that it is above 1100 nm/s.
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53 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

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3 We demonstrated that the combination of a 3D flow-focusing microfluidic reactor, real-time
4 analytics, and numerical simulations, provide meaningful data that resolve the dynamics of the
5 solvent-induced self-assembly of polystyrene-coated gold nanoparticles. The use of a microfluidic
6 device equipped with feeding pumps ensures highly reproducible experimental conditions, as
7 confirmed by online UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy measurements. On-chip SAXS analysis of the
8 entire channel of the reactor provides information on the hydrophobic shell collapse,
9 demonstrating that the thiol-terminated polystyrene of 53 kg/mol grafted on gold nanoparticles
10 surface experiences relatively fast collapse within the range of 100 – 500 nm/s. The knowledge on
11 dynamics of polymer shell and the amount of water at each point of the channel allowed us to
12 estimate the energy potential of the interacting nanoparticles. We found out that the aggregation
13 process of Au@PS nanoparticles starts once the polymer shells are fully collapsed. Our findings
14 support the idea that either kinetically trapped small clusters or larger aggregates can be obtained
15 by the rate of solvent mixing, since the mixing rate determines the interaction potential landscape
16 during solvent-induced gold nanoparticle self-assembly.
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38 METHODS

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40 **Chemicals and Materials.** Tetrahydrofuran (99,9%), N,N-Dimethylformamide ($\geq 99,8\%$) were
41 purchased from ROTH. 3-Aminopropyltrimethoxysilane (97%, APTMS), 3-
42 Glycidyloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (98%, GPTMS), tetrachloroauric acid (HAuCl_4 , $\geq 99\%$),
43 hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, $\geq 99\%$), cetyltrimethylammonium chloride
44 solution (CTAC, 25 wt.% in H_2O), benzyldimethylhexadecylammonium chloride (BDAC, $\geq 99\%$),
45 sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 , $\geq 96\%$), L-ascorbic acid (AA, $\geq 99\%$), were purchased from Sigma-
46 Aldrich. All chemicals were used without further purification. Milli-Q water (resistivity
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3 18.2 M Ω ·cm at 25 °C) was used in all experiments. Kapton® HN sheets (125 μ m) and Kapton®
4 HN (25 μ m) were purchased from DR. DIETRICH MÜLLER GMBH. Transparent PTFE tubings
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6 (inner diameter: 0.37 mm) were purchased from IDEX.
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10 **Characterization.** Optical characterization in batch was carried out by UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy
11 with an Agilent 8453 diode array spectrophotometer. Optical characterization in-flow was
12 performed using a MAYA 2000 pro spectrophotometer (Ocean Optics), equipped with DT-MINI-
13 2-63 light source and 2 optical fiber (QP50-2-VIS-NIP, core diameter: 50 μ m, length: 2 m) and
14 SMA-Z-10-uvol Teflon flow cell with 10 mm optical path. The (*in situ*) SAXS measurements were
15 performed at (U)SAXS beamline ID02 of the ESRF in Grenoble (France) using a Rayonix MX170-
16 HS detector, with a pixel size of 89 \times 89 μ m² and positioned in 10 m distance to the sample.⁴³ The
17 detector covered the range from 0.0063 nm⁻¹ $\leq q \leq$ 0.537 nm⁻¹, which corresponds to structures in
18 the range from 12 to 990 nm. Transmission electron microscopy was carried out using a LaB₆-
19 TEM electron microscope of type JEOL JEM-1400PLUS (40 kV – 120 kV) equipped with a
20 GATAN US1000 CCD camera (2k x 2k).
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35 **Synthesis of polystyrene-coated gold nanoparticles.** First, gold seeds (~1.5 nm) were prepared
36 by reduction of HAuCl₄ (5 mL, 0.25 mM) with NaBH₄ (0.3 mL, 10 mM) in aqueous CTAB
37 solution (100 mM) under vigorous stirring.⁴⁴ An aliquot of seed solution (0.6 mL) was added to a
38 growth solution containing CTAC (100 mL, 100 mM), HAuCl₄ (0.36 mL, 50 mM) and ascorbic
39 acid (0.36 mL, 100 mM). The mixture was left undisturbed for 12 h at 25 °C. The solution
40 containing gold nanoparticles (10 nm) was centrifuged (9000 rpm, 2 h) and redispersed in water
41 to a final gold concentration of 2.5 mM. A dispersion of gold nanoparticles of 10 nm in diameter
42 (0.32 mL, 2.5 mM) was added under magnetic stirring to a growth solution containing BDAC
43 (100 mL, 100 mM), HAuCl₄ (1 mL, 50 mM), and AA (1 mL, 100 mM). After incubation for
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3 30 min at 30 °C, the dispersion was washed twice by centrifugation and redispersed in water to a
4 final gold concentration of 5 mM. A dispersion of gold nanoparticles (2 mL, 5 mM) was added
5 dropwise under sonication to a dispersion of PS-SH (1 molecule of PS-SH per nm² of gold surface)
6 in THF (20 mL). The mixture was left for 15 min in an ultrasonic bath. To ensure ligand exchange,
7 the resulting mixture was left undisturbed for 12 h, and then centrifuged twice (7000 rpm, 30 min).
8 The particles were finally dispersed in THF.
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17 **Microfluidic Reactor.** Multi-layered Kapton-based 3D flow-focusing reactor (main channel:
18 width × height × length = 120 μm × 125 μm × 47.5 mm) with a constrained middle channel in
19 front of the mixing cross (diameter of the spherical cross section: 30 μm) was fabricated using
20 previously described fabrication processes that combined laser ablation^{24,26,28} and covalent
21 bonding of Kapton films.^{26,29,30} The resulting microfluidic Kapton-based device with 3D-flow
22 focusing (see Figure 1B) was connected to the tubing using NanoPort connections that were
23 pressed onto the device using a custom-built aluminum sample holder which featured openings for
24 the X-ray beam as shown in Figure S1.²⁶
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35 **Clustering in flow.** The reactor was coupled to NEMESYS 120 NEM-B100-01E syringe pump
36 system Cetoni equipped with gastight 1700 Series Syringes, Hamilton via PTFE inlet tubings. A
37 degassed solution of Au@PS in THF or DMF was placed in the central inlet, whereas the two side
38 inlets were fed equally with aqueous solutions ($\phi_{sc}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 21 \text{ vol}\%$) of the corresponding solvent
39 (THF, DMF). The outlet of the mixing device was connected to a SMA-Z-10-uvol Teflon flow
40 cell via an outlet tubing (length: 6 cm, inner diameter: 0.37 mm).
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Online optical UV-vis-NIR measurements. The neMESYS UserInterface was used to design the
flow profile. In each experimental cycle of 1 h, the initial $FRR = 0$ was increased stepwise
triggering the self-assembly of the Au@PS by focusing the central stream with a H₂O/THF mixture

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3 from the side channels and maintained for 45 min to obtain statistically-significant spectral data.
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5 Then, the initial conditions of $FRR = 0$ were restored by rinsing the device for 8 min. In each cycle,
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7 the changes in flow rates were performed stepwise (6 steps, 10 s each) to reduce bubble formation,
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9 while maintaining the total flow rate constant, thus providing a constant residence time.
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12 **SAXS measurements in batch.** For standard SAXS measurement, a glass capillary ($\varnothing = 1$ mm,
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14 Müller & Müller OHG Glasbläserei, Germany) was filled with ~ 0.5 mL of the Au@PS dispersion
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16 in THF. The same amount of THF was measured for background subtraction. The acquisition time
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18 for both samples was 0.5 s.
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21 **SAXS measurements in flow.** To align the microfluidic reactor, the vertically and laterally
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23 oriented microfluidic reactor was moved through the beam path (along the y -axis) while
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25 monitoring the pin-diode intensity in front of the detector. The position of the beam spot on channel
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27 was obtained by finding the maximum transmitted intensity at the detector. This procedure was
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29 repeated at ten different horizontal positions (x -axis) along the channel. The acquired scans,
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31 allowed to draw a best-fit line through the identified motor positions, which correspond to the
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33 middle of the channel.
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37 To collect scattering data of in-flow clustering experiments, the microfluidic reactor was mapped
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39 with the X-ray beam. 2D scattering patterns were collected at several downstream positions, x_c ,
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41 (x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{22}) along the mixing channel, beginning at the most downstream position (x_{22}) and
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43 moving towards the mixing cross (x_0 is located in front of the mixing cross) to avoid collection of
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45 data from already exposed sample. Further, seven vertical scans (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_7) were carried out at
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47 each horizontal position leading to each data set consisting of $23 \times 7 = 161$ scans per experiment.
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49 These vertical scans spread over a range of ± 40 μm above and beyond the calculated central
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51 position y_3 . The chosen step length in y of 26.7 μm in combination with the beam size of 48 μm
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3 caused an overlap of 21.3 μm of the neighboring scans. The integration time and the photon flux
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5 were 1 s and $6 \cdot 10^{10}$ photons/s (12.6 keV), respectively.
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8 All background measurements were performed by applying the same flow conditions as for the
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10 clustering experiments using the flow of pure THF. After collecting a corresponding data set, flow
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12 conditions were changed and run for 10 min to ensure stable flow in the microchannel prior to the
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14 acquisition of new scattering patterns.
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17 **UV-Vis-NIR data analysis.** A MATLAB code was developed to analyze and visualize the UV-
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19 Vis-NIR dataset ~ 1200 spectra in 60 min run. First, the raw data were smoothed to decrease the
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21 noise in less intense spectra. Then, reference spectra were used to remove aberrations (*e.g.* spectra
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23 which were taken when large bubbles occupied the entire flow cell) using a Pearson's correlation-
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25 based filter. Remaining spectra were then analyzed by extracting the LSPR position (λ_{max}) and
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27 *FWHM*, using built-in MATLAB functions. The mean values and standard deviations of λ_{max} and
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29 *FWHM* were calculated on selected sections of the acquired data. These were chosen to include at
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31 least 100 spectra to provide significance.
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35 **SAXS data analysis.** Due to direct reflection of the primary beam at the inner channel wall,
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37 vertically aligned streaks occurred in some of the 2D scattering patterns. However, the scattering
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39 data from a standardized integration sector $\pm 45^\circ$ from the horizontal axis (in the q -range 0.05 nm^{-1}
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41 $< q < 0.5 \text{ nm}^{-1}$) was normalized and background-subtracted. Fitting of 1D scattering curves was
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43 carried out by relying on the standard fit library of *Scatter*^{41,45} (homogeneous core and shell model
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45 and Percus-Yevick approximation model⁴⁰).
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52 **Conflict of Interest.** The authors declare no competing financial interest.
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23 **Supporting Information Available.** Calculation of water amount in mixed solution; effect of gas
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25 bubbles and requirement of spectral data processing; additional time-resolved optical experiments
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27 showing the effect of Au@PS and water concentration and solvent exchange on cluster size and
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29 morphology; (static) SAXS reference experiments and fitting of scattering data; theoretical
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31 modelling of the interparticle interaction energy. This material is available as PDF file free of
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33 charge via the internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.
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Time-Resolved Analysis of the Structural Dynamics of Assembling Gold Nanoparticles

Figure 1. Design of a 3D flow focusing reactor for studying nanoparticles self-assembly. a)

Polystyrene-coated gold nanoparticles in THF undergo clustering upon mixing with water in a Kapton[®]-based hydrodynamic 3D flow-focusing reactor. Real-time UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy in flow collects the optical properties of the assemblies at the reactor outlet. On-chip SAXS analysis along the channel (orthogonally to the flow and the lateral focusing directions) allows us to determine time-resolved structural changes of the polymer shell and clustering nanoparticles upon mixing. **b)** Simulated (COMSOL CFD) longitudinal cross-section of the THF/water mixture and dimensions of the reactor. Volumetric flow rates of middle channel (Q_{mc}) and side channels (Q_{sc}).

Figure 2. Online optical UV-vis-NIR and off-chip TEM characterization of clustered gold nanoparticles. **a)** Normalized UV-Vis-NIR spectra in flow, during cyclic clustering by switching the flow rate ratio, FRR between 0 (dispersed) and 2 (aggregated), at a total flow rate of $Q_{tot} = 600 \mu\text{L/h}$. Each spectrum was recorded in an interval of 3 s. **b)** Extracted spectral features of three consecutive clustering cycles between $FRR = 0$ and 2, showing reproducible values of the spectral features. **c)** TEM images of dispersed and aggregated nanoparticles (Scale bars: 200 nm). **d)** Changes of spectral features as a function of FRR showing that $FRR = 0.3$ is the limiting ratio between water and THF. Error bars are standard deviations calculated from 100 data points after flow stabilization. **e)** TEM images of clustered nanoparticles for $FRR = 0.5$ and 4 (Scale bars: 500 nm).

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Figure 3. In situ SAXS characterization of clustering particles. **a-c)** Scattering curves of flow-focused Au@PS obtained at various downstream channel positions x_c under different flow rate ratios ($FFR = 0, 2, 4, 10$, each with $Q_{tot} = 900 \mu\text{L/h}$). The scattering curves were fitted (red lines) using the hard sphere model for disordered particle assemblies (in Percus-Yevick approximation) indicating the occurrence of interparticle interactions. **d)** Scattering curves of reference Au@PS in pure THF ($FFR = 0$) showing unaltered spectral features along the channel. **e, f)** Temporal evolution of the effective particle radius R_{eff} (**e**) and the hard sphere volume fraction η (**f**) along the microfluidic channel at $FFR = 2, 4$ and 10 , respectively. Both fit parameters reach an onset (dashed circles), indicating a fast collapse of the polymer shell. The geometrical parameters were obtained by applying the hard sphere model for disordered particle assemblies (Percus-Yevick approximation).

Figure 4. Mapping interparticle interaction energy over the entire channel length. a) Top view of the longitudinal cross section of a simulated distribution of THF concentration in the channel ($l = 47.5$ mm), at FRR ranging from 2 to 10 and total flow rate of $Q_{tot} = 900$ $\mu\text{L/h}$. **b)** Calculated interaction potential E_{inter} at different channel positions x_c , for FRR = 2, 4 and 10. **c,d)** Primary energy minima, E_{min} , and maxima, E_{max} , obtained from **b)** at different positions along the channel, suggesting that the clustering of Au@PS is favored after full collapse of the polystyrene shell.

Figure S1. Top view of the flow reactor. Kapton[®]-based 3D-flow-focusing microfluidic reactor (center), is embedded in aluminum holder that consists of two halves that are screwed together to press the NanoPort[™]-assembly against the microfluidic chip. The reactor is supplied with three software-controlled syringes (left) that contain the solution of Au@PS (middle) and mixture of water and THF (lateral syringes). The outlet of the reactor is coupled to the flow UV-Vis cuvette connected to two optical fibers.

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Figure S2. UV-Vis-NIR and TEM characterization of mixture containing gold nanoparticles stabilized with thiolated polystyrene in THF.

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Figure S3. Correlation between the applied *FFR* and the final amount of water in the completely mixed solution $\phi_{fin}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ according to Eq. S1.

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Figure S4. Spectral features of an assembly/disassembly cycle in THF **(a)** and DMF **(b)**. At $FRR = 0$ the spectra features exhibit relatively good stability for both solvents. Upon the switch to $FRR = 2$, the nanoparticles clusters leading to LSPR shift and the increase of FWHM. The presence of microbubbles that form upon mixing the water and THF affects the stability of the spectral features. Using DMF as a main solvent prevents formation of microbubbles and thus the fluctuation of the spectral features. Grey bands represent the selected data used for averaging the outcome of the spectral data.

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Figure S5. *upper:* Changes of spectral features as a function of flow rate ratios showing that $FRR = 0.5$ is the limiting ratio between water and DMF. *lower:* TEM images showing clustered nanoparticles produced at different FRR . For large FRR the formation of chain-like aggregates is observed. Flow conditions were equivalent to experiments using THF as solvent (see Figure 2d); $[Au] = 25 \text{ mM}$, $\phi_{sc}(H_2O) = 21 \text{ vol\%}$, $Q_{tot} = 600 \text{ }\mu\text{L/h}$.

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Figure S6. Effect of amount of water **(a)** and Au@PS concentration **(b)** on the optical features of clustering nanoparticles in flow conditions at constant $FRR = 0.5$ and $Q_{tot} = 600 \mu\text{L/h}$. **(a)** Invariance of spectral features for different water vol% in final mixture. To maintain all parameter apart from final water amount constant, the lateral syringes were loaded with mixtures of different THF/water ratio. **(b)** The change of spectral features for different concentration of the nanoparticles. While the lateral syringes contained constant ratio of THF and water, the middle syringe was loaded with THF solution containing different starting concentration of gold.

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Figure S7. 1D scattering curve of capillary SAXS measurement of Au@PS in THF. The curve was fitted with the homogeneous spherical core model (fit parameter: $R_{in} = 22.5 \pm 1.32$ nm; exposure time: 1 s).

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Figure S8. Simulated THF concentration distribution in the 3D flow-focusing mixing channel. The concentrations are shown as a function of the channel width for $FRR = 2, 4$ and 10 (side channel: 21 vol% water) at different downstream positions along the flow direction. In detail, the black curve represents the unmixed THF solution that enters the main channel via the $30 \mu\text{m}$ pore, $x = 0$ corresponds to the middle of the mixing cross and all further curves ($x = 0.5, 1, 2$ and 5) represent positions where SAXS scans were obtained. The width of the grey area equals the width of the X-ray beam along the channel width (y -direction).

Figure S9. Relative standard deviation, σ , of the inner particle radius, R_{in} , for fits of the scattering curves depicted in Figure 3a-d applying the hard sphere ($FRR = 0$) and Percus-Yevick ($FRR = 2, 4, 10$) approximation, respectively. A slight increase of dispersity is observed along the microchannel.

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Figure S10. Estimated evolution of water concentration and hydrophobic parameter along the microchannel. **(a)** Simulated water amount (COMSOL) at the cross-sectional center position in the microchannel at different downstream positions x_c (values extracted from simulations shown in Figure 4a). The simulated flow conditions correspond to *in situ* SAXS experiments at $FRR = 2, 4$ and 10 . **(b)** Hydrophobic parameter f along the entire microchannel calculated from the local amount of water $\phi_{loc}(H_2O)$ (extracted from Figure. S9a) assuming a linear dependence in the region from 5 to 40 vol% water corresponding to the boundaries of f (1 and 0, respectively).

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